

New insights in application of *B. thuringiensis* biopesticides by the whole genome sequencing

Sellami Sameh^{1*}, Zouari Nabil¹, El Abed Fatma¹ and Rouis Souad¹

¹ Laboratory of Biopesticides, Centre of Biotechnology of Sfax, University of Sfax, P.O. Box. “1177”, 3018, Sfax, Tunisia.

* Corresponding author: sellamisameh@gmail.com

Abstract

The bacterium *Bacillus thuringiensis* was recognized for its entomopathogenic activities related to large categories of insecticidal proteins. During a previous study, we obtained nine *B. thuringiensis* strains among 212 from different origins of Tunisia, harboring higher insecticidal activities against three important Lepidopteran pests *Spodoptera littoralis*, *Ephestia kuehniella* and *Tuta absoluta*. These strains were characterized based on the crystal morphology, the gene content and the plasmid profile. During this study, the whole genome shotgun sequencing (WGS) of the nine selected *Bacillus thuringiensis* strains were done in order to have deeper genome information. In fact, this *in silico* study provide more data about the gene expression, protein-DNA interactions, detection of new potential insecticidal proteins for an efficient agricultural pest biocontrol. Based on the MLST classification, the nine strains SS1, SS2, SS3, SS4, SS5, SS7, SS8, SS9 and SS10 were identified as members of the *Bacillus cereus* group.

Introduction

Bacillus thuringiensis is an entomopathogenic, rod shaped, Gram positive, spore-forming and aerobic bacterium found usually in soil, grain dusts, dead insects and water. *Bacillus thuringiensis* belongs to the *Bacillus cereus* group (Jouzani *et al.*, 2017; Palma *et al.*, 2014). *B.thuringiensis* based insecticidal formulations have been recognized as one of the most successful, environmentally safe and sustainable method of controlling insect pests. It is also considered as the most effective bioinsecticide alternative to the harmful chemical insecticides available to man today, owing to its toxicity towards a broad range of insect pests. In fact, dipteran, lepidopteran and coleopteran insect larvae cause intensive damages to growing plants (Jallouli *et al.*, 2020).

During sporulation stage, *B. thuringiensis* produces crystalline inclusion bodies Cry and cytolytic toxins Cyt. These toxins are principally active against lepidopteran species but some show toxicity against coleopteran and dipteran species. Moreover, vegetative cells produce non-crystalline toxins, such as vegetative insecticidal proteins (Vip1, Vip2, Vip3, Vip4), chitinases and secreted insecticidal proteins (Sip), secreted as soluble proteins in a growth medium (Sellami *et al.*, 2018).

Research teams worldwide are in search of *B. thuringiensis* diversity giving more choices of bio-insecticides and alternatives to delay insect resistance. In fact, the discover of new toxins sequences increase the host range of insect pests and avoid the insect resistance problems.

During this study, the whole genome shotgun sequencing (WGS) of the nine selected *Bacillus thuringiensis* strains having important insecticidal activities were done in order to have deeper genome information (gene expression, protein-DNA interactions, detection of new potential insecticidal proteins). This will help us to avoid or delay insect resistance problems and therefore preserve our yield crop's. !

Material and Methods !

Bacterial isolates

Bacillus thuringiensis strains SS1, SS2, SS3, SS4, SS5, SS7, SS8, SS9 and SS10 belong to the bacterial collection of the Laboratory of Biopesticides (Centre of Biotechnology of Sfax, Tunisia). They are isolated from different Tunisian soils and selected among a collection of 212 isolates for their higher insecticidal activities towards *Spodoptera littoralis*, *Ephesia kuehniella* and *Tuta absoluta* (Sellami *et al.*, 2013). Strains were grown at 30°C using LB medium (Sellami *et al.*, 2016).

Sequencing of bacterial genomic DNA

The genomic DNA sequences were obtained via sequencing services provided by MicrobesNG (Birmingham, UK; <https://microbesng.com>). Genomic DNA libraries were prepared with the Nextera XT Library Prep Kit (Illumina, San Diego, USA) according to the manufacturer's protocol, with specific adjustments: the input DNA was doubled and the PCR elongation time was extended to 45 seconds. DNA quantification and library preparation were conducted using a Hamilton Microlab STAR automated liquid handling system (Hamilton Bonaduz AG, Switzerland). The sequencing was performed on an Illumina NovaSeq 6000 sequencer (Illumina, San Diego, USA) using a 250 bp paired-end protocol. Trimmomatic version 0.30 (Bolger *et al.*, 2014) with a sliding window quality cutoff of Q15 was employed to remove adapters from reads. De novo assembly was executed using SPAdes version 3.7 (Bankevich *et al.*, 2012), followed by annotation of contigs using Prokka 1.11 (Seemann, 2014).

Taxonomic nomenclature

In order to classify and identify the nine bacterial strains, the Average Nucleotide Identity (ANI) calculator was performed throughout the calculation of the OrthoANIu percentage

between each strain and 2 reference strains: *Bacillus thuringiensis* serovar *berliner* ATCC 10792 (*Bacillus thuringiensis* reference genome: ASM16161v1; RefSeq: GCF_000161615.1) and *Bacillus cereus* strain (*Bacillus cereus* reference genome: ASM222028v1; RefSeq: GCF_002220285.1). Both reference strains are members of the *Bacillus cereus* group (Yoon *et al.*, 2017). the PubMLST.org website was used to confirm the taxonomic nomenclature (Jolley *et al.*, 2018).

Results

Data availability

The whole-genome shotguns for SS1, SS2, SS3, SS4, SS5, SS7, SS8, SS9 and SS10 have been deposited at DDBJ/ENA/GenBank under accession numbers SUB14008628, SUB14011607, SUB14011636, SUB14011827, SUB14015576, SUB14021476, SUB14021692, SUB14023809 and SUB14028681, respectively. In addition, raw sequence reads have been deposited in the NCBI Sequence Read Archive under BioProject numbers PRJNA1045983, PRJNA1047013, PRJNA1047343; PRJNA1047518, PRJNA1048323, PRJNA1049327, PRJNA1049354, PRJNA1049670 and PRJNA1050135 and run numbers SRR26965796, SRR26993656, SRR27010549, SRR27012744, SRR27034019, SRR27108436, SRR27109226, SRR27128832 and SRR27143901 for SS1, SS2, SS3, SS4, SS5, SS7, SS8, SS9 and SS10, respectively.

Genomic Features

A summary of the genomic features for SS1, SS2, SS3, SS4, SS5, SS7, SS8, SS9 and SS10 is listed in Table 1. The assembling of sequence reads resulted in 57, 95, 176, 122, 194, 169, 59, 76 and 68 contigs for SS1, SS2, SS3, SS4, SS5, SS7, SS8, SS9 and SS10, respectively. In addition, the cumulative contig lengths of the genome assemblies are 6,3 Mb, 6,1 Mb, 6,0 Mb, 6,5 Mb, 6,3 Mb, 5,9 Mb, 5,9 Mb, 6,2 Mb and 6,2 Mb, with a mean coverage of more than 70

X, 57 X, 89 X, 79 X, 74 X, 73 X, 65 X, 49 X and 56 X for SS1, SS2, SS3, SS4, SS5, SS7, SS8, SS9 and SS10, respectively. Besides, all strains have almost equal genomic GC content about 34,68%, 34,79%, 34,87%, 34,80%, 34,75%, 34,89%, 34,76%, 34,83% and 34,76% for SS1, SS2, SS3, SS4, SS5, SS7, SS8, SS9 and SS10, respectively. Furthermore, the tRNA content is also very close between strains about 109, 115, 106, 105, 107, 106, 110, 105 and 104 for SS1, SS2, SS3, SS4, SS5, SS7, SS8, SS9 and SS10, respectively. All strains have one tmRNA and didn't have CRISPR sequence. Moreover, the number of protein-coding genes is almost similar between the nine strains. In fact, the number of CDS for SS1, SS2, SS3, SS4, SS5, SS7, SS8, SS9 and SS10 is 6486, 6285, 6234, 6560, 6505, 6149, 5996, 6336 and 6334 genes, respectively.

Taxonomic classification

The ANI values were determined to identify the taxonomy of SS1, SS2, SS3, SS4, SS5, SS7, SS8, SS9 and SS10 strains (Table 2b). The values were about 96.56%, 96.57%, 96.13, 99.76%, 96.00%, 96.09%, 96.24%, 96.17% and 96.21%, respectively. The submitted genomes of strain SS4, SS9 and SS10 and that of the *Bacillus thuringiensis* reference strain shared 100% sequence identity (Table 2a). This result was confirmed by Ribosomal MLST test (Table 2c) showing the membership of SS4, SS9 and SS10 strains to the species *thuringiensis*. On the other hand, SS1, SS2, SS3, SS5, SS7 and SS8 genomes showed 98%, 96%, 100%, 100%, 100% and 90% sequence identity, respectively with *Bacillus cereus* reference strain. The Ribosomal MLST test confirmed the membership of SS3, SS5 and SS8 strains to the *cereus* species. Nevertheless, the microscopic observation of SS1, SS2, SS3, SS5, SS7 and SS8 strains showed the presence of spherical and cubic crystals. More investigation will be done to confirm the identity of SS1, SS2, SS3, SS5, SS7 and SS8 strains.

Statement on continuing work

The datasets are shared prior to formal publication and should be regarded as preliminary. We strongly encourage and appreciate feedback from the community. For further information, please contact Dr. Sameh Sellami at sellamisameh@gmail.com.

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Table 1: Genomic features of the *Bacillus thuringiensis* SS1, SS2, SS3, SS4, SS5, SS7, SS8, SS9 and SS10 sequenced using Illumina.

Bacterial strain	Number of reads	Contigs (≥ 1 kb)	Largest contig	Total length (bp)	GC (%)	Mean coverage	N50 (bp)	CDS	tRNA	tmRNA	CRISPR	Bioproject	Biosample	GenBank accession	GenBank accession
<i>B.thuringiensis</i> ID2901	1043625	57	1172695	6382739	34,68	70,3736	494293	6486	109	1	0	PRJNA10459 <u>83</u>	SAMN3846 6915	SRR269657 96	SUB1400862 <u>8</u>
<i>B.thuringiensis</i> ID2902	777292	95	618519	6176244	34,79	57,7656	237161	6285	115	1	0	PRJNA10470 <u>13</u>	SAMN3850 8691	SRR269936 56	SUB1401160 <u>7</u>
<i>B. thuringiensis</i> ID2903	1211320	176	224377	6028856	34,87	89,1676	99664	6234	106	1	0	PRJNA10473 <u>43</u>	SAMN3853 0416	SRR270105 49	SUB1401163 <u>6</u>
<i>B. thuringiensis</i> ID2904	1115454	122	1077538	6501121	34,80	79,6897	152939	6560	105	1	0	PRJNA10475 <u>18</u>	SAMN3856 2210	SRR270127 44	SUB1401182 <u>7</u>
<i>B.thuringiensis</i> ID2905	1025967	194	242490	6367332	34,75	74,8089	96557	6505	107	1	0	PRJNA10483 <u>23</u>	SAMN3861 2737	SRR270340 19	SUB1401557 <u>6</u>
<i>B. thuringiensis</i> ID2907	932309	169	224377	5960289	34,89	73,6072	99664	6149	106	1	0	PRJNA10493 <u>27</u>	SAMN3869 2440	SRR271084 36	SUB1402147 <u>6</u>
<i>B.thuringiensis</i> ID2908	841009	59	648327	5996711	34,76	65,1297	198021	5996	110	1	0	PRJNA10493 <u>54</u>	SAMN3869 3318	SRR271092 26	SUB1402169 <u>2</u>
<i>B. thuringiensis</i> ID2909	714071	76	674776	6246516	34,83	49,7058	246187	6336	105	1	0	PRJNA10496 <u>70</u>	SAMN3870 5093	SRR271288 32	SUB1402380 <u>9</u>
<i>B.thuringiensis</i> ID2910	748266	68	749792	6235806	34,76	56,4245	229496	6334	104	1	0	PRJNA10501 <u>35</u>	SAMN3872 5709	SRR271439 01	SUB1402868 <u>1</u>

Table 2: MLST taxonomic nomenclature of SS1, SS2, SS3, SS4, SS5, SS7, SS8, SS9 and SS10. **a)** Predicted taxa; **b)** Average nucleotide identity using FastANI; **c)** Ribosomal MLST (Matching profile)

a)

Rank	Taxon	Support	Taxonomy
SS1	<i>Bacillus cereus</i>	98%	<i>Bacillota</i> > <i>Bacilli</i> > <i>Bacillales</i> > <i>Bacillaceae</i> > <i>Bacillus</i> > <i>Bacillus cereus</i>
SS2	<i>Bacillus cereus</i>	96%	<i>Bacillota</i> > <i>Bacilli</i> > <i>Bacillales</i> > <i>Bacillaceae</i> > <i>Bacillus</i> > <i>Bacillus cereus</i>
SS3	<i>Bacillus cereus</i>	100%	<i>Bacillota</i> > <i>Bacilli</i> > <i>Bacillales</i> > <i>Bacillaceae</i> > <i>Bacillus</i> > <i>Bacillus cereus</i>
SS4	<i>Bacillus thuringiensis</i>	100%	<i>Bacillota</i> > <i>Bacilli</i> > <i>Bacillales</i> > <i>Bacillaceae</i> > <i>Bacillus</i> > <i>Bacillus thuringiensis</i>
SS5	<i>Bacillus cereus</i>	100%	<i>Bacillota</i> > <i>Bacilli</i> > <i>Bacillales</i> > <i>Bacillaceae</i> > <i>Bacillus</i> > <i>Bacillus cereus</i>
SS7	<i>Bacillus cereus</i>	100%	<i>Bacillota</i> > <i>Bacilli</i> > <i>Bacillales</i> > <i>Bacillaceae</i> > <i>Bacillus</i> > <i>Bacillus cereus</i>
SS8	<i>Bacillus cereus</i>	90%	<i>Bacillota</i> > <i>Bacilli</i> > <i>Bacillales</i> > <i>Bacillaceae</i> > <i>Bacillus</i> > <i>Bacillus cereus</i>
SS9	<i>Bacillus thuringiensis</i>	100%	<i>Bacillota</i> > <i>Bacilli</i> > <i>Bacillales</i> > <i>Bacillaceae</i> > <i>Bacillus</i> > <i>Bacillus thuringiensis</i>
SS10	<i>Bacillus thuringiensis</i>	100%	<i>Bacillota</i> > <i>Bacilli</i> > <i>Bacillales</i> > <i>Bacillaceae</i> > <i>Bacillus</i> > <i>Bacillus thuringiensis</i>

b)

Query	Reference Genome (RefSeq)	ANI
<i>Bacillus</i> Strain_2901 fasta_query	GCF_002220285_1_ASM222028v1_genomic_fna_ref	96.5698
<i>Bacillus</i> Strain_2901 fasta_query	GCF_000161615_1_ASM16161v1_BT_fna_ref	96.3922
<i>Bacillus</i> Strain_2902 fasta_query	GCF_002220285_1_ASM222028v1_genomic_fna_ref	96.5789
<i>Bacillus</i> Strain_2902 fasta_query	GCF_000161615_1_ASM16161v1_BT_fna_ref	96.3371
<i>Bacillus</i> Strain_2903 fasta_query	GCF_002220285_1_ASM222028v1_genomic_fna_ref	96.1352
<i>Bacillus</i> Strain_2903 fasta_query	GCF_000161615_1_ASM16161v1_BT_fna_ref	96.004
<i>Bacillus</i> Strain_2904 fasta_query	GCF_000161615_1_ASM16161v1_BT_fna_ref	99.7684
<i>Bacillus</i> Strain_2904 fasta_query	GCF_002220285_1_ASM222028v1_genomic_fna_ref	98.0861
<i>Bacillus</i> Strain_2905 fasta_query	GCF_002220285_1_ASM222028v1_genomic_fna_ref	96.0002
<i>Bacillus</i> Strain_2905 fasta_query	GCF_000161615_1_ASM16161v1_BT_fna_ref	95.8707
<i>Bacillus</i> Strain_2907 fasta_query	GCF_002220285_1_ASM222028v1_genomic_fna_ref	96.0942
<i>Bacillus</i> Strain_2907 fasta_query	GCF_000161615_1_ASM16161v1_BT_fna_ref	95.9454
<i>Bacillus</i> Strain_2908 fasta_query	GCF_002220285_1_ASM222028v1_genomic_fna_ref	96.2497
<i>Bacillus</i> Strain_2908 fasta_query	GCF_000161615_1_ASM16161v1_BT_fna_ref	95.8621
<i>Bacillus</i> Strain_2909 fasta_query	GCF_002220285_1_ASM222028v1_genomic_fna_ref	96.1728
<i>Bacillus</i> Strain_2909 fasta_query	GCF_000161615_1_ASM16161v1_BT_fna_ref	96.0499
<i>Bacillus</i> Strain_2910 fasta_query	GCF_002220285_1_ASM222028v1_genomic_fna_ref	96.2189
<i>Bacillus</i> Strain_2910 fasta_query	GCF_000161615_1_ASM16161v1_BT_fna_ref	96.112

c)

	rST	Genus	Species
SS3	17172	<i>Bacillus</i>	<i>Bacillus cereus</i>
SS4	17305	<i>Bacillus</i>	<i>Bacillus thuringiensis</i>
SS5	17172	<i>Bacillus</i>	<i>Bacillus cereus</i>
SS8	100349	<i>Bacillus</i>	<i>Bacillus sp.</i>
SS9	267076	<i>Bacillus</i>	<i>Bacillus thuringiensis</i>
SS10	113669	<i>Bacillus</i>	<i>Bacillus thuringiensis</i>

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